

Additive manufacturing of hydroxyapatite scaffolds: Fractographic study of gyroid structures with engineered surface roughness

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Abstract

Triply periodic minimal surface (TPMS) structures, particularly gyroids, offer promising mechanical and biological properties for bone tissue engineering. This study presents the fabrication of hydroxyapatite (HA) gyroid scaffolds using digital light processing technology, incorporating engineered surface roughness through the use of burnable porogenic agents—starch and microcellulose. The cytocompatibility and mechanical strength of the prepared scaffolds were evaluated, and the effect of pores in the microstructure on the fracture

mechanism was assessed and compared to theoretical models calculated using finite element analysis. The scaffolds supported cell adhesion, and a significant improvement in cell proliferation was observed with the addition of a higher concentration of starch, while microcellulose showed moderate effects. Compressive strength slightly decreased with increasing porosity, yet remained within the applicable range to withstand physiological loading. These findings demonstrate the potential of HA TPMS scaffolds with tailored surface microporosity and enhanced roughness for fabricating spinal implants.

Keywords

Triply periodic minimal surface; gyroid; DLP 3D printing; hydroxyapatite; fractography

1. Introduction

Triply periodic minimal surface (TPMS) structures, such as gyroids, are increasingly explored in the field of additive manufacturing due to their unique combination of high surface area, tunable porosity, and mechanical isotropy [1-3]. When combined with bioactive ceramics such as hydroxyapatite (HA), these structures form a promising class of materials for bone tissue engineering and regenerative medicine, and are already being used in clinical practice [4]. To promote osteointegration, nutrient transport, and angiogenesis in a gyroid structure, it is favourable to fabricate scaffolds in a bioinspired architecture and engineered surface roughness. Such a design provides a conducive environment for cell attachment, proliferation, and mineralisation, while ensuring efficient mass transport.

Introducing porosity typically reduces the mechanical strength of a material [5]. The architected porous ceramics can circumvent this trade-off through geometric optimisation. TPMS structures distribute mechanical stress efficiently due to their smooth, continuous curvature, which is free from sharp corners and edges that would otherwise concentrate stresses. This can be successfully implemented in the design of spinal implants, where axial compression is the dominant force generated by body weight and muscle activity. Indeed, other biomechanical loads in the spine, such as shear forces, bending moments or torsional loads, must not be neglected [6]. However, axial compression plays an important role and has been extensively studied in the literature, both in relation to TPMS structures and the material nature, where structures based on metals [6-9], polymers [2, 3, 10, 11], or ceramics [12-16] are most commonly fabricated using additive technologies. Studies focusing on ceramic materials, however, remain relatively limited. Guo et al. [12] produced a gyroid structure from hydroxyapatite doped with bioactive glass, achieving a compressive strength of approximately 15 MPa. According to finite element analysis, this structure exhibited significant stress concentrations at joints and load-bearing regions. Isaacson et al. [14] demonstrated that the

compressive strength of gyroid hydroxyapatite structures depends on porosity, with compressive strengths ranging from 0.65 MPa to 4.29 MPa for porosities between 80% and 60%. Similarly, Bouakaz et al. [13] reported a compressive strength of 4.29 MPa for a hydroxyapatite scaffold with 65% porosity and gyroid structure. It is evident that variations in the compressive strength of gyroid scaffolds are influenced not only by overall porosity and material but also by factors such as the volume and density of structural struts, as well as the presence of defects, including micro- and nano-scale pores, processing-induced cracks, and delamination.

It is essential to recognise that numerous scientific studies also focus on the numerical modelling of TPMS structure behaviour under mechanical loading and compare simulation data with experimental results. However, the literature still lacks detailed fractographic investigations identifying fracture origins and mechanisms under axial compression, particularly for brittle ceramic materials, which hold significant potential in regenerative medicine. A comparable analysis is found only in the work of Isaacson et al. [14], where HA gyroid structures fabricated by a combination of viscous extrusion and photopolymerization exhibited fracture initiation at surface cracks (delaminated layers). Moreover, intergranular fractures were observed, and concentric cracks formed due to insufficient curing of the pre-polymer mixture and the development of thermal stresses.

This study aims to fabricate a TPMS structure (gyroid) from hydroxyapatite using additive manufacturing, specifically digital light processing (DLP) technology, while incorporating engineered surface roughness through the addition of a sacrifice phase based on starch and microcellulose directly to the printable suspensions. The resulting multi-porous scaffolds were characterised in terms of their mechanical and biological performance, with uniaxial compressive loading chosen to represent the dominant loading mode in vertebral body

replacement applications. Fracture mechanisms were analysed by combining finite element simulations of the stress state with detailed fractographic examination.

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2. Experimental

2.1 3D printing and suspension preparation

A commercial 3D printer, CeraFab 7500 (Lithoz, Austria), utilising DLP technology with a blue LED light source of approximately 465 nm wavelength, was used for the 3D printing of TPMS gyroid structures. The printed layer thickness was set to 25 μm . The printing suspensions consisted of hydroxyapatite powder (HA, 50 nm, Nanografi, Turkey) calcined at 900 °C for 3 hours and a mixture of acrylates, additives and dispersants. The mixture was milled for 4 hours before being used for 3D printing. Suspensions with the addition of porogenic agents contained potato starch (Belbake, Lidl, Czech Republic) or microcellulose (Celova C500, Weidmann, Switzerland). Porogenic agents in amounts of 1 vol.%, 3 vol.% or 5 vol.% (hereinafter referred to as HA_XY, where X is vol.% and Y is S – starch or C - microcellulose) were added to the mixture prior to milling. The microcellulose was extracted from an alkaline solution (pH \approx 12). The solution was decanted, and the sediment was repeatedly washed by alternating an acidic solution (HCl, 5 mL/100 mL) and a NaOH solution (5 g/100 mL) until the supernatant reached neutral pH. After the final washing step, the microcellulose was filtered and dried at 70 °C for 24 hours, and subsequently added to the prepared suspension. Fig. 1 shows the morphology of HA powder particles, including their phase purity, as well as the morphology of starch particles and microcellulose fibres.

Fig. 1 Micrographs of a) HA powder with its b) diffraction pattern of single-phase as-received HA powder, c) spherical particles of starch and d) fibres of microcellulose.

The printed gyroid-structured scaffolds were cuboids with model dimensions of $7 \text{ mm} \times 7 \text{ mm} \times 10.5 \text{ mm}$, with the ends fitted with a load-spreading plate; see Fig. 2a. The gyroid structure contains S-shape (visible on the left face) and U-shape (visible on the right face) features oriented parallel or transversely to the loading direction, respectively. The effect of feature orientation will be explained later in the context of fracture behaviour. The printed scaffolds were cleaned of unpolymersed suspension by blowing compressed air through the scaffolds and washing them in LithaSol 20 solvent (Lithoz, Austria). Thermal treatment of the scaffolds involved binder removal at $800 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ in a nitrogen atmosphere, without dwell. Samples during binder removal were buried in a bed of active carbon (AY-5, Carbon Link, UK). Subsequently, the samples were annealed at $900 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 10 hours in air to decarbonise the body and then sintered at $1250 \text{ }^\circ\text{C}$ for 2 hours in air.

Fig. 2 Example of a model structure used for 3D printing (a) and corresponding finite element model (b) showing loading force orientation.

2.2 Microstructural characterisation

The bulk density of a gyroid structure with a designed open macro porosity of 66% was measured using Archimedes' method in water, in accordance with the ČSN EN ISO 18754 standard. The external geometry of the scaffolds was observed using a Stemi 508 stereomicroscope (Zeiss, Germany), and the microstructure was examined using scanning electron microscopes Verios 460L (FEI, Czech Republic) and Mira 3 XMU (Tescan, Czech Republic). Porosity between HA grains was evaluated from these microstructure images using morphometric analysis. The phase composition of the HA powder was analysed using the SmartLab 3kW X-ray diffractometer (XRD, Rigaku, Japan) equipped with a Cu K α radiation source operating at 40 kV and 30 mA. Data were collected over a 2θ range of 10° – 110° with a step size of 0.02° . The diffraction pattern was analysed using PDXL software and compared with reference data from the ICDD PDF-4 database (card no. 01-072-1243).

2.3 Biological properties

Bone marrow mesenchymal stem cells (BMSC) were maintained in complete mesenchymal stem cell growth medium supplemented with supplement mix and 5% penicillin/streptomycin (50 U/mL and 50 µg/mL) at 37 °C in a humidified 5% CO₂ incubator. The scaffolds were sterilised for 10 min under UV and kept in culture medium for 20 min prior to cell seeding. Cells were harvested by trypsinisation with a 0.25% trypsin-EDTA solution at 75% confluence and seeded at a density of 1×10^4 cells on the scaffolds, which were placed in a polystyrene microplate. Cell proliferation was evaluated by the colourimetric XTT as recommended by the manufacturer. The water-soluble formazan was measured at 450 nm on day 1 and day 7. All chemicals and BMSC were purchased from Merck, Germany. The data were presented as mean \pm standard error. The statistical analysis was performed using a two-sample t-test with a 95% confidence level.

The BMSC cells on the scaffolds were washed three times with phosphate buffer saline (PBS) and then fixed with 4% paraformaldehyde in PBS for 20 min at room temperature prior to SEM observation. The cells were then dehydrated in a series of increasing ethanol concentrations (50%, 70%, 80%, 90%, and 100%) for 5 min each. Finally, the samples were coated with a 15 nm gold layer.

The fluorescence staining was performed by imaging the cytoskeletal actin fibre organisation and the nucleus at day 3. The fixed cells were permeabilised with a solution of 0.2 % Triton-X 100 for 20 min and then washed in deionised H₂O. The actin fibres and nucleus were stained with ActinGreen™ 488 (Invitrogen™, Thermo Fisher Scientific, USA) for 30 min at room temperature (RT) and DAPI for 5 min at RT, respectively. The nucleus and actin were imaged using a fluorescence microscope (Axio Imager M2m, Zeiss, Germany).

2.4 Mechanical properties

The compressive strength of the gyroid structures was measured using a universal testing machine (Instron 8862, Instron, USA) equipped with a Dynacell load cell with a capacity of 5 kN. Apparent compressive strength was calculated based on the measured dimensions of each specimen after sintering. At least 20 specimens were tested for each material variant. To ensure proper load transfer to the porous gyroid structure of the specimen, 0.5 mm-thick, fully dense load spreading plates were co-printed on each side of the gyroid structure, directly touching the compression plates of the testing machine. The compressive strength tests were performed at a crosshead speed of 0.5 mm/min. The stress-strain curves calculated from load-displacement data obtained during the testing were analysed to determine the compressive strength from the fracture force. The data were statistically evaluated using the Weibull approach, which is suitable for brittle materials, to determine the Weibull strength and modulus via fitting by maximum likelihood method.

2.5 Analysis using the finite element method

The finite element method (FEM) was employed to determine the stress-strain behaviour of the gyroid model structure with load spreading plates to mitigate the compressive strength test. The model used for printing was adjusted for sintering shrinkage and meshed using the GSMH mesh generator within the FEM module of FreeCAD 1.02. The model consisted of more than 300,000 nodes with a minimum size set to 50 μm to ensure sufficient precision. The bottom plate was fully constrained, while a compressive load of 15 MPa—corresponding to the average measured strength of pure HA—was applied to the upper plate. Fig. 2b shows the meshed model used for the simulation. The fully elastic analysis was performed using solver CalculiX, taking into account the Young's elastic modulus of material of 95 GPa, which represents the average value reported in literature for fully dense sintered HA [17]. The maximal principal stress field was

calculated and plotted, and critical places with stress concentration were identified. The visualisation was conducted using ParaView 6.0.1 software.

2.6 Fractographic analysis

Fractographic analysis was performed on the fracture surfaces of specimens following the compressive strength test. Specimens were gold-coated, and a scanning electron microscope (Lyra 3XMU, Tescan, Czech Republic) was used to identify fracture origins.

3. Results and discussion

3.1 3D printing

Fig. 3 Images of TPMS structures after 3D printing fabricated from hydroxyapatite (HA) (a), hydroxyapatite containing 3 vol.% of starch (HA_3S) (b), and microcellulose (HA_3C) (c) combustible porogenic agents.

Gyroid-structured bodies with 66% porosity were printed. During the binder removal process, degradation of starch particles and microcellulose fibres occurred. The porogenic agents were

reported to decompose over the temperature range of 250 °C – 400 °C [18, 19]. Decomposition of porogenic agents results in the formation of pores within the volume and on the surface of printed samples. The burnout of the porogenic agent on the surface of the samples increased surface roughness. The pore shape depended on its source, i.e., elliptical pores were observed for starch and wormhole-like pores for microcellulose fibres.

Fig. 3 shows printed and cleaned scaffolds (a – HA; b – HA_3S; c – HA_3C) after thermal processes. It is evident from the images that the printed HA TPMS structure exhibits high fidelity in replicating the geometric design of the model. A stepped pattern is visible along the line forming the inner edge of the gyroid channel, indicating the horizontal orientation of the printed layers. Compared with scaffolds containing starch and microcellulose, a slight reduction in print quality is observed. The porogenic agents likely increased light scattering during the printing process, resulting in a slight reduction in lateral detail resolution. This is most evident in the poorer definition of layer edges and the slight blurring of the structure's contours. However, the printed structures show no signs of cracking, and the images reveal no evidence of delamination between layers.

Fig. 4 shows the surfaces of printed TPMS structures after sintering. The surface of the HA gyroid scaffolds (see Fig. 4a) was free of major defects or pores; detailed images revealed only intergranular porosity with an average size of $0.76 \pm 0.34 \mu\text{m}$. The increased surface roughness of gyroids from which starch particles were burned out was formed by numerous dimples, as documented in Fig. 4b. A detailed image of a dimple (Fig. 4e) revealed remnants of a crust formed by HA particles, which had coated the original starch particle and remained in the microstructure after its collapse during the thermal treatment. In addition to these large defects, porosity between HA grains was also observed, with an average size of $0.81 \pm 0.30 \mu\text{m}$. A similar average pore size between HA grains, $0.76 \pm 0.39 \mu\text{m}$, was measured in the microstructure of microcellulose-containing samples. As shown in Fig. 3c and Fig. 4c, fine

microcellulose fibres protruded from the surface of the scaffold. The visibility of the fibres was caused by hydroxyapatite particles as a result of thermal treatment of suspension-coated fibres. The surface roughness was influenced by burned-out fibres lying on the scaffold surface and by cavities left by oriented fibres in the layers, as shown in Fig. 4f.

Fig. 4 Surface micrographs of a) HA (HA), b) HA with 3 vol.% starch (HA_3S), c) HA with 3 vol.% microcellulose (HA_3C), and surface details showing captured porosity of d) HA, e) after firing of starch particles, and f) after firing of microcellulose fibres.

During the printing process, the fibre orientation occurred at both steps when the suspension was spread into a thin layer using a blade and during suspension flow at the building platform immersion. Throughout this process, shear forces cause the orientation of particles or fibres in the suspension, as previously reported for tape casting [20, 21]. The same phenomenon occurred in the suspension containing HA and microcellulose fibres. The fibres were oriented parallel to

the layers, as shown in Fig. 5. These oriented fibres did not cross the layers but remained within the ceramic matrix or penetrated the free surface. After thermal processing, wormhole-like pores remained in the microstructure, and cavities were left on the surface.

Fig. 5 Micrograph showing a cross-section of HA_3C (3 vol.% of microcellulose) sample after sintering. White dashed lines indicate the orientation and thickness of the layers.

After sintering, the bodies shrank to final dimensions of 5.2 mm × 5.2 mm × 8.2 mm ($x \times y \times z$). The 3D-printed gyroid structure shrank anisotropically, with shrinkage of 25.9% in the x - and y -axes and 21.4% in the z -axis (building direction). This behaviour is commonly observed in 3D printing and is considered critical for producing dimensionally accurate parts. Anisotropic shrinkage in different axes is most often attributed to layer orientation, density differences between layers, or the formation of thermal gradients due to uneven heating during sintering [22]. In our case, a slight increase in porosity was identified at the interfaces between individual layers. This porosity may arise from several factors, including insufficient light exposure time per layer, high ceramic particle loading, oxygen-induced inhibition of photopolymerization, or reduced shrinkage along the z -axis during the sintering process. However, it did not compromise interlayer adhesion or lead to delamination.

Microstructural analysis revealed a radial porosity gradient, with the outer regions of the cylinder exhibiting significantly fewer pores compared to the core (see Fig. 5). This phenomenon may be attributed to enhanced light penetration and polymerisation near the surface, combined with optical scattering and reduced curing efficiency in the inner regions. Concerning the ceramic phase density, HA gyroids without added porogenic agents reached a 97.4 ± 0.5 % (HA) relative density, while increasing porosity due to higher starch and microcellulose content reduced the relative density to 94.6 ± 0.3 % (HA_5S) and 95.0 ± 0.7 % (HA_3C), respectively. It should be noted that the viscosity of the 5 vol.% microcellulose suspension was too high, leading to 3D printing under non-standard conditions. Therefore, this set of samples was excluded from further experiments.

3.2 Biological response

Fig. 6 Fluorescence imaging of nucleus (DAPI; blue colour) and actin fibres (green colour) in BMSC cells cultured on HA scaffold and HA scaffolds modified with different concentrations of starch or microcellulose at day 3.

The cytocompatibility of HA scaffolds and HA scaffolds with engineered surface roughness was evaluated by assessing cell adhesion, morphology and proliferation. Nuclear staining (blue colour) revealed a uniform distribution of BMSCs within the

scaffold pores, as shown in Fig. 6. Actin staining (green colour) confirmed that the BMSCs were well adhered to and spread across both HA scaffolds and HA scaffolds with modified surface roughness, exhibiting the characteristic elongated spindle-like morphology. SEM imaging reveals a good adaptation of cells to the uneven surface of scaffolds (cavities, ripples, or dimples) caused by starch or microcellulose, as shown in Fig. 7.

Fig. 7 Surface micrographs of a) HA gyroid and HA gyroids with engineered surface roughness caused by b) starch and c) microcellulose.

Proliferative capacity is an important indicator of scaffolds for bone tissue engineering. Quantitative analysis of cell proliferation was performed by evaluating the metabolic activity of BMSC cells using the XTT assay at days 1 and 7. Results demonstrated a significant increase in BMSC metabolic activity on all studied scaffolds at day 7 compared to day 1 (see Fig. 8). When comparing the proliferation rates between days 1 and 7, the HA_1S and HA_1C scaffolds exhibited a proliferation rate comparable to the control HA scaffold, showing approximately a two-fold increase in response at day 7 relative to day 1. In contrast, HA_3S, HA_5S, and HA_3C scaffolds showed an approximately three-fold increase in response compared with the HA control. The difference in proliferation rate between HA_3S and HA_5S scaffolds was negligible. Overall, all tested scaffolds demonstrated good cytocompatibility and the ability to

support cell adhesion and growth. Cells exhibited a characteristic elongated, spindle-shaped morphology and adapted well to the surface inhomogeneities of the modified scaffolds.

Fig. 8 (a) Proliferation assay of BMSC cells on the different scaffolds at day 1 and day 7.

Statistical analysis was performed for the values on the given day. P values reaching statistical significance ($p < 0.05$; $n=3$) between HA and modified HA scaffolds are not labelled. NS* indicates a statistically non-significant difference between HA and modified scaffolds at $p > 0.05$. NS** indicates a statistically non-significant difference between modified scaffolds at $p > 0.05$. (b) The graph illustrates the fold change in cell proliferation from day 1. P values reaching statistical significance ($p < 0.05$; $n=3$) between HA and modified HA scaffolds are indicated by *.

The results of HA gyroid scaffolds are consistent with previous studies on 3D-printed hydroxyapatite scaffolds with TPMS architectures, which have reported enhanced cell viability and proliferation compared to other printed structures [23, 24]. In the case of TPMS HA architecture modified with a higher concentration of starch (HA_3S and HA_5S) and microcellulose (HA_3S), a significant increase in cell proliferation was observed. These results highlight the importance of introducing a higher degree of surface extraposity to enhance cellular proliferative activity, as lower levels of extraposity did not lead to a significant improvement over the HA control. This observation aligns with reports demonstrating markedly improved cell adhesion and proliferation on rougher surfaces compared to smoother ones [25-27]. Moreover, this phenomenon has been observed across materials commonly used in biomedical applications, such as hydroxyapatite, titanium alloys, and bioactive glass [28]. It has been further suggested that surfaces with micro- or nano-texture or porosity promote more extensive cell spreading and firmer anchoring due to a greater number of adhesion sites, improved protein adsorption, and cell orientation in the case of directionally structured roughness, as well as proliferation or differentiation [29, 30]. Consistent with these observations, our SEM images of the modified scaffolds (see Figs. 7b and 7c) revealed cells with well-developed adhesive protrusions, which can mature into stronger and more stable focal adhesions. This may lead to stronger mechanical anchoring and more active cellular communication, including signalling that influences migration, differentiation, and cell survival [31]. In contrast, scaffolds with the lowest concentration of starch and microcellulose (HA_1S and HA_1C) did not enhance cell proliferation, as their cellular responses were comparable to those of the HA control. This finding suggests that the concentration of organics introduced to generate additional extraposity must be carefully optimised in order to improve the surface properties and, consequently, the biological response.

3.3 Mechanical properties

Fig. 9 Dependence of compressive strength of HA TPMS scaffolds on volume of porogenic additives (a) and Weibull plots of compressive strength.

Fig. 9 shows the compressive strength values as a function of the volume of added starch particles or microcellulose fibres, along with the corresponding Weibull plot for the same sets of values. The straight lines provide a fit of the strength data based on the maximum likelihood estimation method, and their slope corresponds to the Weibull modulus. The characteristic strength (σ_0) and the Weibull modulus (m), along with their 90% confidence intervals, were determined in accordance with the EN-843-5 standard and are presented in Table 1. The Weibull modulus reflects the variability in the strength data, while the characteristic strength corresponds to the stress level at which 63% of the specimens are expected to fail. The highest value of characteristic compressive strength, $\sigma_0 = 15.38$ MPa, was achieved by HA gyroids without the addition of any porogenic agent. The addition of starch particles led to a decrease in characteristic compressive strength from 14.06 MPa (HA_1S) to 12.80 MPa (HA_5S). The incorporation of 1 vol.% microcellulose fibres resulted in only a slight reduction to $\sigma_0 = 14.75$ MPa, whereas 3 vol.% caused a significant drop to $\sigma_0 = 12.31$ MPa. This decline in compressive

strength can be attributed to the formation of a multi-porous microstructure resulting from the addition of a burnable phase, as well as to the alignment of wormhole pores perpendicular to the loading direction, which can form larger defects that trigger fracture. As shown in Section 3.1, samples with increasing concentrations of starch or microcellulose exhibited a slight decrease in density, indicating a moderate increase in total porosity. Such a reduction in strength due to porosity is commonly observed in ceramics [32-34]. The fundamental reasons for the decrease in strength with increasing porosity include, in particular, the role of pores as stress concentrators, the increased presence of which increases the probability that some defects will reach a critical size in the loaded area, in this case at the free surface of TPMS structure. If we consider these HA scaffolds with TPMS architecture to be replacements for the trabecular parts of vertebrae, then current studies indicate that the maximum compressive strength of bone tissue in the vertebral bodies of the thoracic and lumbar spine varies depending on age, sex, and bone density, ranging from 2 to 15 MPa in healthy individuals [35, 36]. Therefore, the prepared scaffolds, in terms of compressive strength, appear to be suitable for spinal implant applications.

Table 1 Characteristic strength and Weibull modulus values with their 90% confidence intervals (CI)

Sample	Characteristic strength, σ_0 (MPa)	90% CI for σ_0 (MPa)	Weibull modulus, m (-)	90% CI for m (-)
HA	15.38	[14.48; 16.34]	9.03	[6.03; 13.51]
HA_1S	14.06	[13.18; 15.01]	8.51	[5.60; 12.93]
HA_3S	13.20	[12.22; 14.25]	7.20	[4.67; 11.09]
HA_5S	12.80	[11.67; 14.05]	5.83	[3.86; 8.82]
HA_1C	14.75	[13.63; 15.95]	7.73	[5.02; 11.89]
HA_3C	12.31	[10.94; 13.85]	5.96	[3.52; 10.08]

The Weibull modulus is a statistical parameter that quantifies the variability/scatter in the mechanical strength of brittle materials. In ceramics, a higher Weibull modulus indicates more

consistent mechanical behaviour and a narrower distribution of critical flaws, while a lower value reflects larger scatter and reduced reliability. HA gyroid samples, modified with starch or microcellulose as porogenic agents, exhibit Weibull modulus values ranging from 5.83 to 8.51, see Table 1. The pure HA sample (no porogen) shows the highest reliability ($m = 9.03$), while samples with increasing porogen content show a progressive decline in m . This trend is consistent with the literature, where porosity is known to reduce Weibull modulus due to increased flaw population and stress concentration effects. When considering hydroxyapatite TPMS structures as a whole, the calculated values of the Weibull modulus are slightly higher compared to the data found in the literature [14, 37, 38]. However, the direct comparison is not possible because the fracture behaviour is dependent on factors as the measurement technique, the origin and properties of the HA powder, the design of the TPMS structure (pore morphology, wall thickness, etc.), and the macroscopic quality of the ceramic body determined by the manufacturing technology, which also limits the processing defect sizes.

3.4 Fractographic analysis

Representative fracture surfaces of TPMS gyroid structures formed during the compressive test of HA specimens are shown in Fig. 10. The first row presents overall views of typical brittle failure sites in the gyroid structure after compressive loading for both structure to loading direction configurations, i.e., S-shape in Fig. 10a and U-shape in Fig. 10b, as representatives of typical loading cases. Details of crack initiation sites are also provided to allow identification of fracture origins (marked with arrows). Fig. 10c illustrates additional phenomena observed during fractographic analysis, specifically the mutual arresting of cracks.

In the fracture surfaces of the HA gyroid sample without added porogen (see Figs. 10a and 10b), a relatively smooth surface of the 3D structure was observed, with internal porosity ranging from 1.8 to 5.4 μm of equivalent sphere diameter. Finer pores were located closer to

the sample surface. The origin of crack initiation in these relatively well-sintered samples is not entirely apparent. However, detailed microstructural images of the initiation sites reveal that the cracks consistently originate from the surface. The critical defects are likely to be artefacts caused by the 3D printing process, as is commonly reported for additively manufactured materials. [32]. The fracture process during compressive loading of the gyroid structure appears to be very complex due to the variety of locations of concentrated tensile stresses, which are distributed across the structure's surfaces and surrounded by spots of compressive stress. The probable overall fracture mechanism is multiple crack initiation, which corresponds to the fractographical observations (see Fig. 10a). Several fracture initiation areas are observed on the surface of HA (S-shaped features oriented in the loading direction). Two selected areas of multiple initiation are shown in detail (fracture origins marked). On the contrary, when the structure feature is U-shaped (horizontally oriented to the loading direction), only one fracture initiation point is usually identified. The presence of a single initiation point is likely related to the height-to-width ratio of the specimen. This results in a higher occurrence of multiple stress concentration spots in S-shaped features than in U-shaped ones. Interestingly, the fracture structure also revealed multiple sites where propagating cracks were mutually arrested when they crossed (see Fig. 10c). This was likely due to the complex design of the gyroid structure, together with the presence of obstacles in the form of compressive stresses and already propagating cracks.

In the fracture surfaces of samples with induced multi-porosity and surface roughness, crack propagation was initiated from the surface or near the surface pores, (see Fig. 11a). The initiation sites were identified as the remains of burnt starch particles that had formed a rough surface, as shown in Fig. 4b, or clusters of individual pores, ranging from 7.2 to 50.4 μm in diameter, located near the surface. The influence of localised stress concentration near the surface is shown in Fig. 11a, where a small surface-touching pore is identified as a fracture

origin, although a significantly larger pore lies in its vicinity. Surprisingly, no pore coalescence in the form of ligament fracture between pores was observed, a commonly reported phenomenon [39]. Fig. 11b shows a fracture site that likely contains multiple crack initiation points, one of which is a characteristic cavity left by a burned-out microcellulose fibre.

In conclusion, crack propagation occurred predominantly from the surface of the gyroid structure, with sites formed by burned-out porogenic phases contributing to this behaviour. The observed multi-porous structure is the reason for the decrease in the Weibull modulus with increasing porogen concentration. No fracture due to delamination of printed layers was observed, indicating a well-controlled HA 3D printing process.

Fig. 10 Microphotographs of fracture surfaces of TPMS HA scaffold showing a) S-shaped feature (oriented in the loading direction), U-shaped feature (horizontally oriented to the loading direction) and c) mutual arresting of cracks. Detailed images (I, II, and III) show fracture origins marked by orange and red arrows.

Fig. 11 Microphotographs of fracture surfaces of TPMS HA scaffolds with induced multiporosity and surface roughness using starch particles (a) or microcellulose fibres (b). Detailed images (IV and V) show fracture origins, marked by orange arrows.

3.5 Numerical simulations

A numerical simulation was conducted using FEA to identify critical regions and relate these to the results of fractographical analysis. The overview of the results from the fully elastic analysis, presented as the maximal principal stress, is shown in Figs. 12a and 12b. The analysis

revealed areas of stress concentration – dark areas, where the peak stress level reached approximately 160 MPa in tension and almost 150 MPa in compression. The calculated stresses correspond well with the typical bending strength of fully dense HA [40]. Two distinct geometrical features (described as S and U-shape features) can be recognised in the TPMS structure, each characterised by pronounced stress concentration regions. While the vertical S-shaped features exhibit stress concentrations on their convex surfaces, the U-shaped features show stress concentrations on both the convex and concave surfaces, as illustrated in Fig. 12c and 12d, respectively. The maximum stress concentration is not located exactly at the geometric centre of the bend of the feature, but is slightly eccentric due to the lack of complete symmetry in the structure. This corresponds well with the fracture origins found during fractographic analysis (see Figs. 10 and 11).

Further, the stress situation within the body of the TPMS gyroid structure was analysed, and Figs. 12e and 12f show the stress concentration for the central middle planes. Clearly, the stresses are slightly lower (approximately 120 MPa in tension and 43 MPa in compression) than those found on body surfaces, where geometric stress concentrations at the free edges are a factor. Therefore, most crack initiations can be expected in the vicinity of the body surface. Additionally, the presence of multiple regions with the same stress concentration can lead to multiple crack initiation and crack stopping in regions of compressive stresses. This mechanism is valid only for the initial moments of crack propagation, as subsequent cracks will redistribute stress. Multiple crack initiations were observed on the fracture surfaces (see Fig. 10a), as well as cracks that crossed and terminated (see Fig. 10c). This confirms the complex stress state that led to the TPMS gyroidal structure's relatively high resistance to catastrophic failure.

Fig. 12 Distribution of Maximal Principal Stress of loaded TPMS HA scaffold side overview (a, b), details of features (c, d) and cut in the central plane showing situation in the middle of the HA scaffold body (e, f). Geometrical features oriented vertically – S-shape – (a, c, e), and oriented horizontally – U-shape – (b, d, f).

4. Conclusions

Hydroxyapatite gyroid scaffolds fabricated via DLP and modified with starch or microcellulose porogens exhibit a favourable combination of biological and mechanical properties for use in vertebral body replacements. Engineered surface roughness supported cell adhesion and improved proliferation, particularly in the case of starch-modified scaffolds. Compressive strength of starch-modified microstructure remained high enough to withstand physiological loads in the spinal area. Crack propagation in TPMS gyroid HA structures predominantly initiates at surface defects, often linked to 3D printing artefacts or burned-out porogenic phases. Fractographic analysis revealed that S-shaped features exhibit multiple crack initiation points due to higher stress concentration, while U-shaped features typically show a single initiation site. Therefore, the fracture behaviour can be particularly controlled by the design of the TPMS structure. Samples with added porogens displayed clusters of pores (7.2–50.4 μm) and increased surface roughness, which further promoted crack initiation, reducing the strength and Weibull modulus. Numerical simulations confirmed stress peaks of ~ 160 MPa in tension and 150 MPa in compression at surface regions, which correlate with the initiation sites in the tested samples. Despite these stress concentrations and complex crack interactions, the gyroid design demonstrated preserved high strength even in porogen-modified variants, validating its use for biomedical applications.

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CRedit authorship contribution statement

Daniel Drdlik: Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation. **Eliska Siska Viragova:** Investigation. **Premysl Stastny:** Investigation, Writing – review & editing. **Katarina Drdlikova:** Writing – review & editing. **Zdenka Fohlerova:** Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Investigation. **Klara Castkova:** Funding acquisition. **Zdenek Chlup:** Writing – original draft, Writing – review & editing, Methodology, Investigation.

Declaration of competing interest

The authors declare that they have no known competing financial interests or personal relationships that could have appeared to influence the work reported in this paper.

Data availability

The data supporting the findings of this study are openly available on Zenodo at the following link: <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18163125>.

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